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The strong and united voice of universities
of science and technology in Europe

Union of Skills: Building a strong science and technology base for a competitive and prosperous Europe

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CESAER, the strong and united voice of over 50 leading universities of science and technology in Europe, welcomes the European Commission's ambition to strengthen Europe's human capital in science and technology, as outlined in the [Union of Skills](#) and [A Competitiveness Compass for the EU](#).

Universities of science and technology recognise their roles and responsibilities in equipping Europe with the scientific knowledge and talent needed to reinforce the continent's global position in advanced science and technologies—an essential foundation for competitiveness, resilience, and prosperity. They are already fulfilling this role and stand ready to scale up their contributions in partnership with EU institutions, member states, industry, and other societal actors.

What sets universities apart is their distinctive ability to combine the generation of new scientific knowledge with its teaching and real-world application, thereby integrating education, research, and innovation. Within this landscape, universities of science and technology stand out for their dual commitment to pursuing fundamental scientific understanding and addressing societal priorities through technological advancement. Their strong dedication to frontier research, technological development, and societal application equips them to tackle complex challenges, drive transformative innovation, and contribute to Europe's competitiveness and prosperity. These universities do not simply transmit scientific knowledge; they create new insights and involve students as active participants in dynamic communities of inquiry at the forefront of science and technology.

This deep integration of knowledge creation and transmission positions universities of science and technology at the forefront of Europe's transformations, particularly in the advanced science and technologies that underpin competitiveness, prosperity, and resilience.

To reinforce Europe's global position, we recognise the urgency of the challenge and the need to significantly raise the level of ambition and support. This requires a decisive step change—particularly at the European level. The EU institutions must place universities at

the core of strategies for human capital that serve as a cornerstone of competitiveness and prosperity, particularly in advanced science and technologies. These institutions must be empowered through clear, stable, and forward-looking legislative and funding frameworks.

Researchers, innovators, teachers, and students must be supported through ambitious, excellence-driven programmes that promote long-term talent development at the frontiers of science and technology. These programmes should support the integration of research, education, and innovation across the full knowledge triangle. The Union of Skills initiative has a vital role to play in this regard. For example, its STEM Education Strategic Plan—which aims to reverse the decline in STEM performance and attract more students to STEM pathways and careers—is a welcome step forward. The Union of Skills should serve as a key enabler of the skills and talent that underpin Europe’s global position as a leader in advanced science and technologies, both today and in the future.

In summary, the [Union of Skills needs education and research at its heart](#).

To achieve this, we outline five key areas where the EU institutions must act decisively:

1. investing in people and ideas to boost competitiveness through frontier research and research-based education;
2. co-creating and expanding ecosystems in strategic sectors to integrate talent development with innovation;
3. attracting and retaining top academic talent by improving career pathways and mobility;
4. advancing inclusive and ethical STEM education to broaden and future-proof the talent pool;
5. empowering universities in governance and policy design to ensure legitimacy, coherence and long-term success.

1. Invest in people and ideas to strengthen competitiveness

Europe’s competitiveness and prosperity depend on attracting and developing the brightest minds, and enabling them to pursue excellent, high-risk and long-term research and innovation. Supporting research-based education and frontier science must therefore be at the centre of implementing the Union of Skills. The EU must ensure that education and skills policy go beyond short-term labour market matching to also serve broader societal missions and long-term innovation needs.

Too often, funding instruments prioritise short-term political priorities at the expense of frontier science and researcher-driven research and foundational education. Yet transformative technologies—such as AI, mRNA vaccines or quantum computing—almost always originated from research led by researchers themselves.

Universities of science and technology offer a unique environment where disciplinary depth and interdisciplinary collaboration coexist. This ecosystem is essential for training the engineers, scientists, and innovators of tomorrow. Sustained investment in this environment will support Europe as a global hub for innovation and address the grand

challenges of our time, from climate change and energy transitions to digital sovereignty and health resilience.

We call on EU institutions to:

- Prioritise long-term investment in research-based education and frontier science to ensure global competitiveness and innovation capacity.
- Substantially expand European flagship funding programmes for research, innovation, training and mobility — including Horizon Europe, Erasmus, and their successors — as key instruments for delivering the Union of Skills. Meeting the urgency and scale of the challenge requires a level of ambition that entails at least doubling the budget for the successor to Horizon Europe and tripling that of Erasmus.
- Reinforce bottom-up, excellence-based programmes such as Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) and European Research Council (ERC), preserving their exclusively open and field-agnostic nature.
- Balance top-down and bottom-up funding across Horizon Europe, Erasmus+ and their successors, and avoid making funding contingent on rigid skills taxonomies or short-term market expectations.
- Support continuous education, reskilling and upskilling in strategic sectors in advanced science and technologies through close collaboration with universities of science and technology.
- Strengthen support for academia-industry partnerships, including through collaborative research, a [revitalised EIT](#), [enhancing PhD cooperation with industry](#) and initiatives such as the [European Universities alliances](#) supported by EU funding, enhancing interconnections between university outcomes and talent with industry needs, and bringing the latest industry insights and problem formulations into university education and research.

2. Co-create and expand ecosystems in strategic sectors

Europe’s leadership in strategic fields like clean technologies, AI, microchips, aerospace, and defence relies on robust, agile knowledge and innovation ecosystems. Universities of science and technology act as system integrators by combining talent development, cutting-edge research, infrastructure, and partnerships to drive competitiveness and prosperity.

The integrated education and research of universities of science and technology — including undergraduate, master’s, doctoral, lifelong learning, and alternative professional learning pathways co-developed with private and public partners — ensure flexibility and responsiveness to evolving regional, national, and European needs. Industrial doctorates, apprenticeships, and continuous professional development opportunities deepen academia-industry links, enhance societal and economic impact, and equip candidates to solve real-world challenges vital to Europe’s global positioning in advanced science and technologies. By uniting each institution’s strengths, universities co-develop state-of-the-art joint programmes that share staff, expertise, resources, and infrastructure. These initiatives equip students with the unique competencies required of the [Engineers of the Future](#) (2024).

These universities also lead mission-oriented research for and with society, translating discoveries into socio-economic impact and anchoring innovation ecosystems locally, while contributing to Europe’s wider strategic goals through international consortia and partnerships (e.g. European Universities alliances).

We call on EU institutions to:

- Leverage the leadership of universities of science and technology as key drivers of Europe’s prosperity, resilience, and competitiveness in priority sectors, notably in advanced technologies.
- Empower universities of science and technology as integral drivers and system integrators within education, research, and innovation ecosystems, collaborating with industry and other non-academic partners, to accelerate talent development, technology development, and diverse professional learning pathways, including joint international programmes, apprenticeships, flexible industrial doctorates, and lifelong learning opportunities through the Union of Skills.
- Expand cross-border, interdisciplinary collaboration and advanced training partnerships that fully integrate the knowledge triangle of education, research, and innovation. This includes strengthening accessible, seamless progression pathways from vocational to academic education, reskilling initiatives, and embedding online, hybrid and blended education as a core component of inclusive learning ecosystems.

3. Retain and attract top academic talent in science and technology through stable careers and open mobility

To secure Europe’s competitiveness and prosperity, we must provide our researchers, educators and innovators — as well as new talent beyond our borders — with attractive, secure and flexible [career paths](#), underpinned by university autonomy and stable, adequate funding.

The EU must urgently address persistent barriers related to immigration, visas and precarious career conditions, particularly for top talent in science and technology—as highlighted in our report [Research careers: A critical choice for Europe](#) (2024). This includes tackling the growing bottleneck faced by early-career researchers entering permanent academic careers. We welcome the Commission’s commitment to removing such barriers, and this must be matched by tangible support measures, including visa reform and binding national funding targets underpinning the establishment of stable academic positions, by working together with national governments and funding agencies. Swiftly advancing the implementation of the Council recommendations on a [European framework to attract and retain research, innovation and entrepreneurial talents in Europe](#) and [Attractive and sustainable careers in higher education](#) is essential.

Retaining and attracting top talent in science and technology requires adequately funded higher education systems across Europe at national level, and significantly reinforced

funding instruments at European level. Proven programmes with a strong track record in attracting and retaining talent—particularly in science and technology—must be expanded. An excellent starting point is the recommendation in the [Align, act, accelerate](#) report (2024), which recommends ensuring that all proposals evaluated as excellent under Horizon Europe are funded through a combination of EU, structural and national funds (e.g. via ‘Seals of Excellence’). We strongly endorse this recommendation and urge its swift implementation, and this would be a decisive step in the right direction.

At national level, we reiterate our long-standing call—set out in [Sustainable Funding for Universities of the Future in Europe](#) (2020)—for the establishment of enforceable GDP-based targets across Europe: for research and innovation, and for higher education, in line with the best performers in the world.

We call on EU institutions to:

- Fully fund—through a combination of EU, structural and national funds (e.g. via ‘Seals of Excellence’)—all high-quality proposals under Erasmus+ and Horizon Europe, especially talent-focused instruments such as MSCA and Erasmus Mundus.
- Involve universities and academics in shaping the forthcoming Visa Strategy and Integration Plan.
- Set binding GDP investment targets for research and higher education, and enforce them in cooperation with member states.
- Establish co-funding schemes for secure, high-quality academic positions, especially targeting early-career researchers, see [‘Research careers: A critical choice for Europe’](#) for details.
- Develop European career progression frameworks that recognise both research excellence and educational contributions. In addition to structural support measures, transparent, predictable, and diverse career paths are necessary. The EU should support the advancement of European career grid models for academics that recognises teaching performance, transfer competence, and supervision as well as research output.

4. Advance future-proof, inclusive and ethical STEM education

Declining basic skills, especially in mathematics, and persistent gaps in upper secondary STEM education pose growing challenges for universities of science and technology. Tackling these issues upstream in the education system is essential to secure Europe’s long-term competitiveness and prosperity.

This futureproof competitiveness depends on maximising the talent pool and fostering excellence and diversity in STEM education. The STEM Education Strategic Plan must be complemented by supporting action at university level, including support for STEM didactics and teaching careers.

Sustainable STEM education requires new didactic approaches that combine technical excellence with social responsibility. Formats such as real-world laboratories, participatory

teaching concepts and living labs empower students as co-creators of innovation and should be actively promoted at European level.

We welcome initiatives such as STEM Futures and Girls Go STEM, and underline that broader inclusivity efforts are needed, including support for students from lower socio-economic backgrounds, migrants and rural areas. At the same time, universities need robust and stable funding to further strengthen teaching capacity, develop innovative pedagogies, and promote ethics in STEM education.

Fostering ethical literacy alongside technical proficiency is a hallmark of European education. Integrating topics such as AI ethics, sustainability, human rights and civic responsibility into STEM curricula prepares future professionals to develop technologies that serve society responsibly. Universities of science and technology are already leading this integration and should be supported as models for ethical, inclusive and forward-looking education.

We call on EU institutions to:

- Work with member states to raise STEM standards in schools, ensuring all students acquire strong foundations for higher education and future careers. This should include an in-depth analysis of the decline in basic skills and the development of effective, coordinated responses at national and European levels.
- Support research-informed teaching practices in STEM higher education, building on frontrunner universities’ expertise.
- Ensure that STEM education initiatives support and are sufficiently connected to higher education, in addition to schools and VET.
- Support continuous training and recognition for academic teachers, particularly in STEM didactics, by working with universities.
- Expand inclusivity efforts to address underrepresentation across all groups.
- Promote ethical engineering and responsible innovation as a hallmark of European education in science and technology, using specific formats and teaching methods such as Responsible Research and Innovation, Service Learning, real-world laboratories, living labs and other participatory teaching models that empower students as co-creators of innovation.

5. Empower universities in governance and policy design

The Union of Skills and the Competitiveness Compass rightly emphasise the need for labour market responsiveness and strong industry involvement. However, it is vital to ensure sufficient representation of universities in key governance structures to ensure these goals are achieved. If universities are not meaningfully involved, policy design and implementation will lack the depth, legitimacy and feasibility required for long-term success.

Universities of science and technology operate at the intersection of research, education, and innovation, and play a fundamentally different role in society than industry. They are

not merely training providers, but mission-driven institutions that generate and transmit scientific knowledge, build critical thinking, train the leaders of tomorrow and support democratic resilience. Their full participation in governance is essential to ensure coherent and effective policies that serve the public good, anticipate future skills needs through scientific and technological foresight, and enable Europe to be a leader.

Governance structures must therefore empower universities as strategic partners and co-creators of policy—not as afterthoughts or implementers of predefined agendas. This is especially urgent in light of the proposed integration of European Education Area governance under the Union of Skills. Effective and inclusive governance must reflect the knowledge triangle and support long-term, system-wide planning. Universities bring unique expertise, long-term vision, and academic freedom, all of which are critical for future-proof, adaptable and innovation-enabling policies underpinned by scientific and technological foresight.

Developing a STEM competence framework and taxonomy within the ESCO classification can serve as valuable connectors between academia, industry, and both immediate and long-term societal needs. While ESCO maps skills to occupations, the interconnection must be reciprocal—insights from both the labour market and universities should inform the framework. This ensures alignment between industry needs and universities' forward-looking perspectives and foresight capabilities, supporting European competitiveness and prosperity in a strategic way.

Academic involvement from the outset fosters shared ownership, improves quality, and strengthens agility in responding to emerging scientific trends and technologies. Without it, there is a real risk of policies becoming overly prescriptive, detached from educational realities, and ultimately ineffective.

We call on EU institutions to:

- Guarantee formal and systematic representation of universities of science and technology in Union of Skills governance, including the European Skills High-Level Board and STEM Executive Panel.
- Ensure governance structures maintain a clear distinction between education and labour market policy domains, reflecting their distinct objectives and logics, with interconnections as appropriate.
- Empower universities as co-creators of skills policy, recognising their strategic role in providing forward-looking, futureproof perspectives in science and technology.
- Involve university leaders and academic staff directly in shaping policy agendas and implementation roadmaps for both education and skills.

Conclusion and our offer

The Union of Skills presents a vital opportunity to safeguard Europe's future competitiveness and prosperity through strategic investment in people, scientific knowledge and technology. Science and technology are among the most powerful forces shaping our societies: they influence how we understand the world, how we live and interact, and how we tackle the complex challenges of our time. Amid rapid and often

disruptive change, they offer not only tools to navigate uncertainty, but also pathways to build more sustainable, equitable and resilient futures.

Universities of science and technology are therefore essential to the Union of Skills. The EU must empower them as full partners—for implementation as well as for governance and in the design of relevant policy and funding instruments.

CESAER stands ready to contribute expertise, evidence and experience to support the successful advancement and implementation of the Union of Skills and its initiatives, including the STEM Education Strategic Plan. We are committed to working closely with the European Commission, member states and key stakeholders to realise a vision of Europe as a global leader through excellence in science, technology and human capital.

Our Members are frontrunners in science and technology and education—well positioned to help develop the frameworks, degrees, careers and ecosystems Europe needs. We offer our full support to help shape future policies and funding instruments, pilot strategic initiatives, and ensure the Union of Skills delivers lasting impact for generations to come.

For more information and enquiries, please contact our Advisor for Benchmark & Higher Education, [Touko Närhi](#).

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